

LECH BOROWIEC¹

Notes on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Corfu Island, Greece

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^{1,2} Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław, Przybyszewskiego 65,
51-148 Wrocław, Poland,
e-mail: ¹lech.borowiec@uwr.edu.pl, ²sdsalata@gmail.com

Abstract: Sixty five ant species collected from 53 sampling sites were recorded from the Corfu Island (Ionian Islands). The checklist includes eight morphospecies not assigned to any formally described taxon. *Temnothorax italicus* CONSANI & ZANGHERI, 1952 is recorded from Greece for the first time. Additionally, the ant fauna of Corfu is compared with three other large Ionian Islands – Cephalonia, Lefkada and Zakynthos.

Key words: ants, Greece, Ionian Islands, Corfu, faunistics, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Corfu is a Greek island located in the Ionian Sea and is the second largest and northernmost of the Ionian Islands. The northeastern edge of Corfu faces the coast of Sarandë, Albania and is separated from the mainland by strait varying in width from 3 to 23 km. The area of the island is 592.9 km² (610.9 km² including adjacent islets) and it runs 64 km long, with greatest breadth at around 32 km. Its coastline measures 217 km. The island is very diverse, a large mountainous plateau is located in the northern part of the island and its highest peak is Mount Pantokrator reaching 911 metres. Other four large hills are placed in the inland and reach around 400-550 meters. However, only Mount Pandokrator has developed deforested alpine zone, while remaining hills are entirely overgrown with Mediterranean forest dominated by *Quercus ilex*. Central and southern parts of Corfu are dominated with extensive agricultural plains rich in streams that do not dry up even in summers. Additionally, there are two moderately large lagoon lakes located on the northeast and southwest coasts: smaller northern Lake Antiniotissa (188 ha), and larger southern Lake Korisson (427 ha). Large parts of Corfu, especially in the northern part, are covered by olive plantations. As the traditional agriculture did not allow pruning of olive trees, many of these plantations resemble natural habitats. The form to which these plantations developed made them shaded semi-forests with trunks often covered with vines, especially *Hedera helix*. Clusters of cypress trees are also common in the olive plantations. The coast has a predominantly cliff character and is usually covered with Mediterranean shrubs. Due to this high environmental diversity, Corfu has the least Mediterranean character among the large Ionian Islands.

So far, there is no work focused exclusively on the myrmecofauna of Corfu. The only single data inputs can be found in faunistic contributions covering wider areas or descriptions of new taxa. The largest number of species for this island was reported by BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013) who noted 17 species new to the Ionian Islands. These records are repeated in present work with some corrections and updates of status of some species. The bulk of the present list is based on the material collected by the first author, and is supplemented by the unpublished records of few other colleagues.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to the sweep net on the roadsides and forest. Nests were searched in rocks cracks and searched on cracked rocks using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% ethanol. Images of ant specimens were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 and Nikon SMZ 18 stereomicroscopes, Nikon D5200 photo camera and Helicon Focus software. List of localities and taxa in list of collected species are arranged alphabetically. Distribution in Greece refers to BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA and BOROWIEC (2018) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. Geographical coordinates are given in decimal system. The fauna of Corfu ants was compared with myrmecofaunas of other large Ionian islands, based on data from DCGA. This approach excluded doubtful or invalid, due to the recent taxonomic changes, literature records. Almost all of the records in DCGA come from the first author's field collecting trips, and were collected using the same techniques and exploration times of 1-2 weeks (except Lefkada which was explored only during one day trip). Materials are deposited in the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (in temporary deposit by DBET – Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław, Poland – coll. L. Borowiec) and in the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

- 01 – Acharavi loc. 1, 2 m, 1, 3 and 5 VII 2011, 39.793 N / 19.819 E, beach area, leg. W. Żyła;
- 02 – Acharavi loc. 2, 10 m, 4-9 VII 2011, 39.793 N / 19.819 E, olive plantation, leg. W. Żyła;
- 03 – Acharavi loc. 3, 10 m, 8 VII 2011, 39.793 N / 19.819 E, hotel garden, leg. W. Żyła;
- 04 – Ag. Anna, 414 m, 8 VI 2013, 39.7043 N / 19.73766 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 05 – Ag. Ilias, 191 m, 10 VI 2013, 39.79367 N / 19.87508 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 06 – Ag. Martinos, 170 m, 8 VII 2011, 39.788 N / 19.848 E, olive plantation, leg. W. Żyła;
- 07 – Ag. Mattheos, 252 m, 9 IX 2020, 39.49297 N / 19.86921 E, roadsides with *Quercus ilex* forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 08 – Ag. Spiridon loc. 1, 3 m, 7 VII 2011, 39.817 N / 19.857 E, olive plantation, leg. W. Żyła;
- 09 – Ag. Spiridon loc. 2, 13 m, 19 VII 2011, 39.7918 N / 19.8181 E, beach area, leg. Trichas & Kardaki;
- 10 – N of Ag. Stefanos, 88 m, 5 VI 2013, 39.76338 N / 19.65213 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 11 – Ag. Stefanos, 8 m, 5 and 10 VI 2013, 39.75733 N / 19.64634 E, urban area, leg. L. Borowiec;

- 12 – Akr. Kefali n. Ag. Stefanos, 13 m, 5 VI 2013, 39.75194 N / 19.63272 E, mediterranean shrubs, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 13 – Ano Pavlina, 396 m, 9 IX 2020, 39.5091 N / 19.86137 E, roadsides with mediterranean shrubs, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 14 – 1.1 km W of Aspiotades, 21 m, 11 IX 2020, 39.72289 N / 19.70133, the edges of the stream overgrown by reed and herbs, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 15 – Chalikounas beach n. Korission Lake, 9 m, 18 VII 2011, 39.453 N / 19.8757 E, beach area, leg. Trichas & Kardaki;
- 16 – Chorepiskopi-Valanio rd. loc. 1, 86 m, 10 IX 2020, 39.74407 N / 19.74995, old olive trees overgrown by *Hedera helix*, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 17 – Chorepiskopi-Valanio rd. loc. 2, 107 m, 10 IX 2020, 39.72748 N / 19.75334, the edges of the stream overgrown by *Hedera helix*, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 18 – Chorepiskopi-Valanio rd. loc. 3, 150 m, 10 IX 2020, 39.73027 N / 19.75743, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 19 – Corfu town, 10 m, 3 VIII 2002, 39.62667 N / 19.915 E, urban area, leg. G. Bračko;
- 20 – Dassia, 5 m, 4 VIII 2002, 39.68333 N / 19.83333 E, small forest, leg. G. Bračko;
- 21 – Dassia – Hotel Magna Graecia area, 23 m, 11 IX 2020, 39.67588 N / 19.83756, hotel garden, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 22 – Doukades, 174 m, 8 VI 2013, 39.70075 N / 19.75055 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 23 – Ipsos, 1 m, 27 VII 2004, 39.69833 N / 19.3833 E, garden, leg. G. Bračko;
- 24 – Kassiopi, 5 m, 2 IX 2012, 39.78333 N / 19.91666 E, beach area, leg. R. Hofer;
- 25 – Kato Garouna, 350 m, 9 IX 2020, 39.53834 N / 19.85666, small gorge across old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 26 – Kiprianades, 95 m, 8 IX 2020, 39.74032 N / 19.76909 E, the edges of the stream, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 27 – Klimatia loc. 1, 311 m, 6 VI 2013, 39.74123 N / 19.78953 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 28 – Klimatia loc. 2, 290 m, 8 IX 2020, 39.7414 N / 19.78638 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 29 – Lake Andinotissa, 3 m, 9 VI 2013, 39.81662 N / 19.86035 E, sea coast, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 30 – Mt. Pandokrator loc. 1, 736 m, 7 VI 2013, 39.74749 N / 19.86375 E, mountain pastures with rocks, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 31 – Mt. Pandokrator loc. 2, 748 m, 6 IX 2020, 39.73221 N / 19.84825 E, roadsides with *Quercus ilex* forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 32 – Mt. Pandokrator loc. 3, 785 m, 19 VII 2011, 39.7438 N / 19.8714 E, alpine zone with limestone rocks and pastures, leg. Trichas & Kardaki;
- 33 – Mt. Pandokrator, road to Profiti Iliia, 766 m, 6 IX 2020, 39.74951 N / 19.86886 E, mountain pastures with rocks, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 34 – road to Nymfes, 194 m, 9 VI 2013, 39.7524 N / 19.78245 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 35 – Nymfes loc. 1, 162 m, 6 VI 2013, 39.75478 N / 19.79535 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;

- 36 – Nymfes loc. 2, 181 m, 8 IX 2020, 39.75347 N / 19.79617 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 37 – east of Nymfes, 179 m, 9 VI 2013, 39.75047 N / 19.8057 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 38 – Nymfes waterfall, 158 m, 8 IX 2020, 39.75076 N / 19.80541 E, deep humid gorge with stream, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 39 – Old Perithia, 467 m, 10 VI 2013, 39.76159 N / 19.87412 E, old mountai village with gardens, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 40 – Paleokastritsa, 20 m, 2 VIII 2002, 39.67167 N / 19.70167 E, small forest, leg. G. Bračko;
- 41 – Petaleia, 650 m, 4 VIII 2002, 39.75 N / 19.83333 E, shrubs with stones, leg. G. Bračko;
- 42 – Roda, 3 m, 5 VII 2011, 39.788 N / 19.794 E, on flowers, leg. W. Żyła;
- 43 – Sgourades, 400 m, 2 VIII 2002, 39.73333 N / 19.81667 E, small forest, leg. G. Bračko;
- 44 – Sidari, 1 m, 5 VIII 2002, 39.79667 N / 19.7 E, sandy cliff, leg. G. Bračko;
- 45 – Strinilas, 632 m, 7 VI 2013, 39.73963 N / 19.84265 E, deciduous forest, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 46 – Troumpetas , 2.5 km after Alimmatades, 20 VII 2011, 280 m, 39.6832 N / 19.8165 E, leg. Trichas & Kardaki;
- 47 – rd. Troumpetas-Sokraki loc. 1, 447 m, 7 IX 2020, 39.71009 N / 19.7509 E, rocks with mediterranean shrubs, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 48 – rd. Troumpetas-Sokraki loc. 2, 486 m, 7 IX 2020, 39.71018 N / 19.75822 E, *Quercus ilex* forest with mediterranean shrubs, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 49 – rd. Troumpetas-Sokraki loc. 3, 449 m, 7 IX 2020, 39.71385 N / 19.76123 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 50 – rd. Troumpetas-Sokraki loc. 4, 449 m, 7 IX 2020, 39.71606 N / 19.77883 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 51 – Valanio, 150 m, 10 IX 2020, 39.73443 N / 19.76041, shadow humid valley, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 52 – Vistonas, 422 m, 8 VI 2013, 39.68549 N / 19.71453 E, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec;
- 53 – 700 m SE of Vistonas, 385 m, 11 IX 2020, 39.68736 N / 19.70094, old olive plantation, leg. L. Borowiec.

LIST OF COLLECTED SPECIES

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 07, 13, 18, 21, 25, 26, 28, 36, 49, 50, 51.

Note: The species was recorded from Cyclades, Dodecanese, the Eastern Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

Aphaenogaster epirotes (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 09, 30, 32, 35, 39, 45.

Note: The species was recorded from the Eastern Aegean Is., the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Aphaenogaster muelleriana WOLF, 1915

Localities: 22, 27, 32, 34, 37, 39, 40.

Note: *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* is a western species, recorded from the Ionian Islands, western Macedonia, Epirus and the Peloponnese.

Aphaenogaster subterranea (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 04, 05, 18, 27, 30, 31, 37, 38, 51.

Note: The species was recorded from the Cyclades, the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. In our work, we classified all samples with large body size, stout head, a partly pale body colouration, and reduced microreticulation on the posterior part of the head as *A. subterranea*. This morphospecies is common in very humid to mesic deciduous forests. However, its conspecificity with the true *A. subterranea* is under study. Molecular and biometric data suggest that populations of *A. subterranea* auct. from Europe represent at least eight taxa, seven of them occurring in Greece (our unpublished data).

*Aphaenogaster cf. subterranea*_COR (Fig. 4)

Localities: 27, 35.

Note: This is a member of a complex of at least three undescribed Greek endemic morphospecies of the *Aphaenogaster subterranea* species group. Revision of this complex is now in preparation.

Aphaenogaster subterraneoides EMERY, 1881

Localities: 30, 46.

Note: The species was recorded from all insular regions of Greece. Specimens from the sample 30 were also noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Bothriomyrmex communista SANTSCHI, 1919

Localities: 12, 30, 39, 41, 45.

Note: Common species, recorded from Dodecanese, the Eastern Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Camponotus aethiops (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 01, 02, 04, 07, 08, 10, 11, 12, 14, 17, 18, 20, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 34, 37, 39, 46, 48, 49, 52, 53.

Note: Common species recorded from Crete, Cyclades, Dodecanese, the Eastern Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, Thrace.

Camponotus dalmaticus (NYLANDER, 1849) (Fig. 1)

Localities: 04, 05, 07, 12, 16, 17, 25, 27, 34, 36, 37, 39, 40, 42, 45, 46, 47, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53.

Notes: Recorded from most of Greek regions except Crete, Cyclades and Dodecanese, it is most common in western parts of Greece. Specimens from the sample 12 were noted in a revision of the *Camponotus lateralis* group by SEIFERT (2019).

Camponotus fallax (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 01, 10.

Note: The species was recorded from the East Aegean Is., the Ionian Is., Macedonia,

Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Specimens from the sample 10 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Camponotus gestroi EMERY, 1878

Localities: 27, 30, 39.

Notes: The species is known from all provinces except Epirus. In Greece occur its two morphoforms considered formerly as subspecies: *C. gestroi gestroi* EMERY, 1878, recorded from northern and western regions of Greece, and *C. gestroi creticus* FOREL, 1886, recorded from southern and south-eastern parts of the country. Because there is a visible morphological transition between these two subspecies we consider it as a cline and do not treat them as valid subspecies. Populations from Corfu belong to the nominotypical form.

Camponotus heidrunvogtae SEIFERT, 2019 (Fig. 2)

Localities: 04, 06, 27, 28, 30, 35, 37, 47, 49.

Note: The species was recently described and morphologically is close to *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825). Specimens noted in the original description came from Bosnia and Hercegovina, Croatia, Montenegro and Greece including our specimens from Corfu collected from the localities 27, 30 and one sample from Central Macedonia (SEIFERT 2019). In our collection we have also a single sample of this species from Epirus.

Camponotus ionius EMERY, 1920

Locality: 40.

Note: Common Greek species recorded from most regions, except Crete.

Camponotus lateralis (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 02, 04, 05, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 36, 37, 39, 45, 49, 50, 51.

Note: The commonest Greek species of *Camponotus* recorded from all regions. Specimens from the samples 12, 22 and 28 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013) under name *Camponotus honaziensis*. According to the SEIFERT (2019) European populations with setose antennal scape and propodeum represent only an infraspecific variation of widespread *C. lateralis* and are not conspecific with *C. honaziensis* KARAMAN & AKTAÇ, 2013 which is endemic to Turkey. Specimens from the sample 27 were included in SEIFERT (2019).

Camponotus piceus (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 02, 06, 10, 12, 14, 17, 22, 26, 27, 28, 30, 36, 39, 42, 51, 52.

Note: The species was recorded from Crete, the Cyclades, Dodecanese, the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Specimens from the sample 27 were noted in a revision of *Camponotus lateralis* group (SEIFERT 2019).

Camponotus vagus (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Locality: 02.

Note: The species was recorded from the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Cardiocondyla dalmatica SOUDEK, 1925

Locality: 01.

Note: Seifert (2003), in the revision of several species groups of the genus *Cardiocondyla*, treated *Cardiocondyla dalmatica* as a junior synonym of *C. elegans* EMERY, 1869. However, a clear clustering based on morphometric data and zoogeographical arguments (SEIFERT 2018) allow a separation of *C. dalmatica* as a parapatric eastern sibling species of *C. elegans*. *Cardiocondyla elegans* is known from Iberia, France, and Italy while *C. dalmatica* occurs from Asia Minor, across the Balkans west to NW Italy and north to Hungary. In Greece *C. dalmatica* was recorded as *C. elegans* from Crete, Dodecanese, Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

Cataglyphis nodus (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 01, 02, 08, 27, 29, 31, 44, 48, 49, 51.

Note: Common species, recorded from most of the regions, except Cyclades and with one doubtful record from Crete.

Colobopsis truncata (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 07, 14, 16, 17, 20, 23, 27, 51.

Note: Common species, recorded from most regions, except Cyclades.

Crematogaster schmidtii (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 02, 04, 07, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 36, 38, 39, 40, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 53.

Note: Common species, known from all Greek regions.

Crematogaster sordidula (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 12, 23, 27, 29, 37, 52.

Note: Common species, known from all Greek regions.

Dolichoderus quadripunctatus (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 07, 14, 16, 20, 23, 26, 27, 37, 38, 51.

Note: The species was recorded from the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Formica gagates LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 04, 27, 35, 37, 45, 48.

Note: The species was recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese a, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Specimens from samples 04 and 35 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Hypoponera eduardi (FOREL, 1894)

Locality: 14.

Note: Invasive species recorded from Aegean islands, Crete, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia and the Peloponnese.

Lasius alienus (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 21, 50.

Note: Common species, recorded from most regions.

Lasius bombycina SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016

Localities: 06, 10, 27, 35, 37, 43.

Note: The species was recorded from Crete, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Is., the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Specimens from samples 10, 27, 35, 37 were noted as *Lasius paralienus* in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013). Revision of the *Lasius paralienus* complex by SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI (2016) divided European and Turkish samples into three distinct species. Our examination of samples from Greece showed that populations from Corfu belong to *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016.

Lasius brunneus (LATREILLE, 1798)

Locality: 30.

Note: The species was recorded from the East Aegean Is., the Ionian Is., Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, the Peloponnese and Thrace.

Lasius illyricus ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 04, 10, 11, 12, 14, 17, 25, 26, 27, 32, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 46, 47, 50, 51.

Note: The species was recorded from Crete, Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. Specimens from samples 10, 11, 35 and 37 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Lasius lasioides (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 04, 22, 23, 27, 30, 32, 39, 45.

Note: Common species, recorded from all regions. Specimens from samples 04, 22 and 45 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Lepisiota frauenfeldi (MAYR, 1855)

Localities: 10, 19, 23, 27, 35, 37, 39.

Note: Common species, recorded from most regions, except Cyclades.

Lepisiota melas (EMERY, 1915)

Localities: 10, 12, 28, 30, 31, 33, 39, 52.

Note: Balkan species, in Greece recorded from most regions, except Epirus and Thrace.

Lepisiota nigra (DALLA TORRE, 1893)

Localities: 12, 27.

Note: The species was recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands and Sterea Ellas.

Linepithema humile (MAYR, 1868)

Locality: 01.

Note: Invasive species, in Greece noted only from Crete, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas exclusively from urban areas and tourist resorts.

Liometopum microcephalum (PANZER, 1798)

Localities: 02, 23.

Note: The species was recorded from the Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Messor ibericus SANTSCHI, 1931

Localities: 02, 10, 11, 14, 17, 20, 21, 22, 23, 27, 28, 30, 32, 39, 41, 52.

Note: The *Messor structor* group was revised recently (STEINER *et al.* 2018) and without doubts *Messor ibericus* is known from Crete, Dodecanese, Epirus, Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly but probably occurs in all regions. Specimens from samples 02, 10, 11, 20, 22, 23, 27, 30, 32, 39, 41 and 52 were noted in preliminary revision of Greek *Messor* (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2019 b)

Messor wasmanni KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 01, 02, 07, 12, 19, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 33, 35, 39, 41, 48, 52.

Notes: The commonest Greek member of the genus *Messor* recorded from all regions.

Monomorium monomorium BOLTON, 1987

Locality: 23.

Note: Probably tramp Mediterranean species recorded from Crete, the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is. and the Peloponnese. In Greece noted mostly from tourist resorts and anthropogenic habitats.

Myrmecina graminicola (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 27, 38.

Note: The species was recorded from all Greek regions except Aegean islands.

Myrmica hellenica FINZI, 1926

Localities: 20, 23, 26.

Note: The species was recorded from the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese and Thrace.

Pheidole cf. pallidula

Localities: 02, 03, 04, 06, 07, 10, 12, 13, 14, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 34, 36, 40, 41, 47, 49.

Note: Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of them recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016), but this revision is still under discussion owing to the great local variability of this very common Mediterranean ant. Material examined by B. Seifert suggests that in Ionian islands occurs *Pheidole balcanica* SEIFERT, 2016.

Plagiolepis peperamus SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 11, 45.

Note: The species is known from all regions, but in Ionian Islands was collected only in anthropogenic habitats. That could suggest that it is an introduced species on these islands.

Specimens from the sample 45 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013) under name *Plagiolepis pallescens* due to misinterpretations of some names within the European members of this genus. This problem was clarified by SALATA *et al.* (2018). Recently, SEIFERT (2020) synonymized *P. perperamus* with *P. atlantis* SANTSCHI, 1920 based on subtle morphometric analysis. It appears that he ignored the large geographical disjunction separating populations from north-western Africa and these known from the Balkan Peninsula and Turkey. Such a disjunctive distribution pattern, as proposed by Seifert, is unknown to any Mediterranean ant species so far. Additionally, in the diagram presented in his revision the Greek samples create a distinct and separate cluster. It is unfortunate that the samples from eastern Mediterranean are underrepresented. Perhaps studies supplemented with more robust material could result in different conclusions. Unfortunately, the separation based on morphometrical formulas proposed by SEIFERT (2020) leads to very confusing results, even when specimens from the same nest sample are measured. Thus, we decided to preserve the name *P. perperamus* for Balkan populations. We do not rule out the possibility that the Northwest African populations may be conspecific with the Balkan ones, but this hypothesis, in our opinion, requires further and more detailed investigation.

Plagiolepis pygmaea (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 04, 07, 10, 12, 13, 18, 21, 23, 27, 28, 30, 34, 39, 45, 48, 52, 53.

Note: Very common species recorded from all Greek regions.

Plagiolepis xene STÄRCKE, 1936

Locality: 27.

Note: It is a social parasite of other *Plagiolepis* species missing worker caste. Recorded from the Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia. Specimens from the sample 27 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Ponera coarctata (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 04, 45.

Note: The species was recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace.

Prenolepis nitens (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 04, 27, 12, 22, 32, 34, 39, 51.

Note: It is a local forest species known from most Greek regions, except Crete, Cyclades and Dodecanese.

Solenopsis cf. lusitanica

Localities: 04, 07, 10, 14, 18, 24, 28, 30, 35, 36, 39, 40, 45, 48, 50.

Note: The status of most of the European species of the genus *Solenopsis* requires extensive revision. GALKOWSKI *et al.* (2010) redescribed *Solenopsis fugax* and suggested that European and Mediterranean species can be grouped into four distinct species. The authors also suggested that several taxa proposed by BERNARD (1950) are probably synonyms, but they did not take any formal nomenclatural decisions. The samples from Corfu, characterized by short and sparse hairs on the mesosoma and small gynes, belong to the *Solenopsis lusitanica* group as proposed by GALKOWSKI *et al.* (2010).

Stigmatomma denticulatum ROGER, 1859

Locality: 47.

Note: Rare species recorded mostly from insular regions, except Cyclades, in Greek mainland known from Epirus, the Peloponnese and Thrace.

Strongylognathus dalmaticus BARONI URBANI, 1968

Locality: 39.

Note: The species was recorded from four regions but only records from the Ionian Island and the Peloponnese are reliable. Specimens from the sample 39 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

*Tapinoma cf. erraticum_BALC**

Localities: 04, 14, 17, 20, 21, 22, 23, 30, 31, 32, 35, 39, 41, 45.

Note: According to B. Seifert's note in WAGNER *et al.* (2018) populations of *Tapinoma erraticum* in south-eastern Europe consist of a complex of two similar species easily separated by the morphology of male genitalia. They suggest that the true *T. erraticum* is common only in northern parts of the Balkan Peninsula. In the material from Greece we found only morphospecies identified by WAGNER *et al.* (2018) as *Tapinoma cf. erraticum_BALC*. Examined specimens come from Crete, the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Is., Epirus, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Temnothorax affinis (MAYR, 1855)

Locality: 39.

Note: The species was recorded from the Aegean Islands, the Cyclades, the Ionian Is., Macedonia, Sterea Ellas and Thrace, but a recent study of *Temnothorax* from Greece suggests that most records are probably misidentifications. We have confirmed records only from the Ionian Islands, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Specimens from the sample 39 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Temnothorax brackoi SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 04, 05, 07, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 22, 25, 27, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39, 45, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52.

Note: It is a recently described species, recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. Specimens from samples 05, 11, 12, 22, 27, 35, 37, 39, 45, 52 were noted in its original description (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019 a).

Temnothorax clypeatus (MAYR, 1853)

Locality: 10.

Note: Rare species recorded only from Aegean Islands and Ionian Islands. Specimens from the sample 10 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013)

Temnothorax cf. exilis (Fig. 5)

Localities: 13, 15, 27, 30, 31, 39, 47, 52.

Note: The *Temnothorax exilis* complex from Greece needs revision. There are at least 7 morphospecies of unclear taxonomic status collected in this country. Specimens from Corfu

belong to the morphospecies with mostly shiny surface of head and pronotum and bicoloured body. This morphospecies is common in Greece, recorded from all regions.

Temnothorax italicus CONSANI & ZANGHERI, 1952

Locality: 17.

Note: The species was recorded from Italy, Slovenia and Croatia. New to the Greek fauna.

*Temnothorax cf. kemali**

Locality: 37.

Note: This is an undescribed species belonging to the *Temnothorax graecus* group. Its description is in preparation. Previously recorded as *Temnothorax graecus* or *Temnothorax cf. graecus* from the Ionian Islands and Thessaly by BOROWIEC & SALATA (2012, 2018b), as *Temnothorax cf. bulgaricus* from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017b) and as *Temnothorax cf. kemali* from Sterea Ellas (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018).

Temnothorax laconicus Csösz *et al.*, 2013 (Fig. 6)

Localities: 04, 05, 12, 21, 22, 25, 30, 34, 35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 45, 47, 40, 51.

Note: It is a recently described species recorded from the Ionian Islands and the Peloponnese. Specimens from samples 12, 27, 30, 35, 37, 39 and 45 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Temnothorax morea Csösz, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018

Localities: 04, 30, 45, 49.

Note: It is a recently described species. Specimens from samples 04 and 30 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013) as *Temnothorax cf. interruptus* sp. 2 and in the original description of this species (Csösz *et al.* 2018).

Temnothorax muellerianus (FINZI, 1922)

Localities: 30, 39.

Note: Social parasite, on Korfu found in nests of *Temnothorax cf. nigriceps*_ION. Widely spread in Greece, recorded from most regions except the Aegean Islands, Cyclades, Dodecanese and Thrace. Specimens from both samples were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

*Temnothorax cf. nigriceps*_ION* (Fig. 3)

Localities: 30, 39.

Note: Specimens from the sample 39 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013) as *Temnothorax nigriceps*. Our study of various samples from Greece of *Temnothorax nigriceps* complex showed that population from Ionian Islands probably represent another undescribed species. This problem will be clarified in a forthcoming revision of this group of species.

Temnothorax rogeri EMERY, 1869

Localities: 04, 22, 27, 39, 52.

Note: Western species, recorded from Epirus, Ionian islands, the western Peloponnese

and western Sterea Ellas. Specimens from samples 04, 27 and 39 were noted in BOROWIEC and SALATA (2013).

Tetramorium diomedeam EMERY, 1908

Locality: 32.

Note: The species was recorded from most Greek regions except Cyclades, Sterea Ellas and Thrace.

Tetramorium immigrans SANTSCHI, 1927

Locality: 19.

Note: Recent revision of the members of the *Tetramorium caespitum* complex of Europe showed that Greek populations belong to six species (WAGNER *et al.* 2017). *Tetramorium immigrans* is common in Mediterranean Europe and Central Europe, north to southern Poland. It was recorded mostly in anthropogenic habitats what can suggest that it is a tramp species. In Greece the species was recorded from all mainland regions, Aegean Islands, Ionian Islands and Crete. Specimens from the sample 19 were noted in the paper on focused on the distribution of Greek *Tetramorium* (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2019 c).

Tetramorium impurum (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 30, 39.

Note: In Greece the species is known from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

Tetramorium kephalosi SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 02, 04, 11, 13, 14, 22, 23, 27, 28, 30, 33, 35, 39, 41, 45, 46, 47, 49, 52.

Note: Recent revision of Balkan members of the *Tetramorium semilaeve* complex showed that Greek populations recorded hitherto under name *T. semilaeve* belong to a different species, described as *Tetramorium kephalosi* (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017). This species is very common in Greece, known from all regions.

*Tetramorium cf. punctatum**

Locality: 45.

Note: There are at least two Greek morphospecies with characters of workers similar to those assigned to *Tetramorium punctatum* SANTSCHI, 1927, which is known from Italy (SANETRA *et al.* 1999). Nevertheless, gyne characters of Greek taxa suggest that both species are not conspecific with the true *T. punctatum*. A proper identification of species of this group requires complete nest samples, with workers, gynes and males. Since we did not collect males in Greek samples, their taxonomical status needs further studies. We have samples of this morphospecies from the East Aegean Is., the Ionian Is., the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly.

DISCUSSION

Ant fauna of Corfu is moderately rich in species and represents 70.6% of all species known from the Ionian Islands (92 species). In this region, the higher number of species (68 spp./73.9%) is known only from Cephalonia, which is the largest of Ionian Islands (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014). Lefkada, the smallest of the four large Ionian Islands, hosts

only 20 species (21.74%), but such a low number can be a result of small sampling effort as this island was investigated only once, during a one day trip in September 2016. Zakyntos, probably due to smaller area, lack of high mountains and more homogenous habitats, holds a smaller number of species when compared with Corfu and Cephalonia (46 spp./50%) (Table 1). The species reported from Corfu represent a mixture of more northern in distribution, associated with shady and humid habitats (i.e. *Aphaenogaster epirotes*, *Camponotus piceus*, *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus*, *Lasius bombycina*, *Myrmecina graminicola*, *Myrmica hellenica*, *Temnothorax affinis*), and strictly Mediterranean species that prefer open and warm habitats or Mediterranean shrubs (i.e. *Camponotus heidrunvogtae*, *Cardiocondyla dalmatica*, *Cataglyphis nodus*, *Crematogaster sordidula*, *Messor wasmanni*, *Stigmatomma denticulatum*, *Temnothorax brackoi*, *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis*, *Tetramorium kephalosi*). There are also few alpine species (i.e. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*, *Strongylognathus dalmaticus*). The data collected so far indicates that one species may be endemic (*Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea* COR). As on all Greek islands with well-established tourists services, the island is colonized by several tramp and invasive species (i.e. *Hypoponera eduardi*, *Linepithema humile*, *Monomorium monomorium*, *Tetramorium immigrans*). Particularly alarming is the presence of highly invasive species *Linepithema humile* (SALATA *et al.* 2019), being destructive for the native ant fauna. Corfu is the only know Greek locality with confirmed presence of *Temnothorax italicus*, however this discovery is not a surprise. *Temnothorax italicus* was described from Italy and later reported from Croatia and Slovenia, this distribution indicated that it could be expected in northwestern Greece.

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Tab. 1. Species collected recently on four largest Ionian islands (COR – Corfu, LEF – Lefkas, CEP – Cephalonia, ZAK – Zakynthos, * – probably undescribed species; species recorded from all four islands in bold).

Species	Island			
	COR 610.90 km ²	LEF 333.58 km ²	CEP 786.58 km ²	ZAK 405.55 km ²
<i>Aphaenogaster balcanica</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Aphaenogaster epirotes</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Aphaenogaster</i> cf. <i>epiotes</i> _SOU*	-	-	+	+
<i>Aphaenogaster muelleriana</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Aphaenogaster subterranea</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Aphaenogaster</i> cf. <i>subterranea</i> _CEP*	-	-	+	-
<i>Aphaenogaster</i> cf. <i>subterranea</i> _COR*	+	-	-	-
<i>Aphaenogaster subterraneoides</i>	+	-	-	+
<i>Bothriomyrmex communista</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Camponotus aethiops</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Camponotus dalmaticus</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Camponotus fallax</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Camponotus gestroi</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Camponotus heidrunvogtae</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Camponotus ionius</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Camponotus kiesenwetteri</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Camponotus lateralis</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Camponotus ligniperdus</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Camponotus nitidescens</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Camponotus oertzeni</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Camponotus piceus</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Camponotus vagus</i>	+	-	+	-

Species	Island			
	COR 610.90 km ²	LEF 333.58 km ²	CEP 786.58 km ²	ZAK 405.55 km ²
<i>Cardiocondyla mauritanica</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Cataglyphis nodus</i>	+	+	-	+
<i>Colobopsis truncata</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Crematogaster ionia</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Crematogaster schmidti</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Crematogaster sordidula</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Dolichoderus quadripunctatus</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Formica fusca</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Formica gagates</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Hypoponera eduardi</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Lasius alienus</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Lasius bombycina</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Lasius brunneus</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Lasius flavus</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Lasius illyricus</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Lasius lasioides</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Lasius turcicus</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>Lepisiota frauenfeldi</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Lepisiota melas</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Lepisiota nigra</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Linepithema humile</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Liometopum microcephalum</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Messor ibericus</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Messor cf. semirufus_GRE*</i>	-	+	+	-
<i>Messor wasmanni</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Monomorium monomorium</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Myrmecina graminicola</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Myrmica hellenica</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Pheidole cf. pallidula</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Plagiolepis pallescens</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Plagiolepis perperamus</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Plagiolepis pygmaea</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Plagiolepis xene</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Ponera coarctata</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Ponera testacea</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Prenolepis nitens</i>	+	+	-	+
<i>Proformica oculatissima</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Solenopsis cf. lusitanica</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Stigmatomma denticulatum</i>	+	-	+	+

Species	Island			
	COR 610.90 km ²	LEF 333.58 km ²	CEP 786.58 km ²	ZAK 405.55 km ²
<i>Strumigenys argiola</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Tapinoma cf. erraticum_BALC*</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Tapinoma festae</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Tapinoma simrothi</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>Temnothorax affinis</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Temnothorax brackoi</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Temnothorax bulgaricus</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Temnothorax clypeatus</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Temnothorax cf. exilis</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Temnothorax flavicornis</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Temnothorax graecus</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Temnothorax italicus</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Temnothorax cf. kemali*</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Temnothorax laconicus</i>	+	+	+	-
<i>Temnothorax messiniaensis</i>	-	-	+	+
<i>Temnothorax morea</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Temnothorax muellerianus</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Temnothorax cf. nigriceps_ION*</i>	+	+	+	-
<i>Temnothorax parvulus</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Temnothorax rogeri</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Temnothorax strymonensis</i>	-	+	+	-
<i>Tetramorium breviscapus</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Tetramorium diomedeam</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Tetramorium immigrans</i>	+	-	-	+
<i>Tetramorium impurum</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Tetramorium kephalosi</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Tetramorium cf. punctatum*</i>	+	-	+	+
<i>Trichomyrmex perplexus</i>	-	-	+	-
Number of species: Total 92	65	20	68	46

Figs. 1–6. Interesting species of ants occurring on Corfu Island: 1 – *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER), minor worker, 2 – *Camponotus heidrunvogtae* SEIFERT, minor worker, 3 – *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_ION, 4 – *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*_COR, 5 – *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis*, common morphotype from Corfu, 6 – *Temnothorax laconicus* CsÖSZ *et al.* (scale bar = 0.5 mm).

Figs. 7–8. *Temnothorax italicus* (CONSANI), species new to Greece: 7 – worker dorsal, 8 – worker lateral (scale bar = 0.5 mm).

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